

**EFFECTS OF FIBRE SURFACE TREATMENT AND
TEST TEMPERATURE ON MONOTONIC AND FATIGUE PROPERTIES
OF CARBON FIBRE EPOXY CROSS PLY LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

The effect of fibre surface treatment on the damage accumulation behaviour of carbon fibre epoxy cross ply laminates has been studied in monotonic and fatigue loading at room temperature. The surface treatments involved were untreated, half, standard and double treatment. For standard treatment fibres the effect of test temperature between -40°C and 100°C has also been investigated. Preliminary results on temperature effects are also presented as a function of surface treatment levels. The damage accumulation behaviour was found to vary significantly as a function of both surface treatment and test temperature.

Keywords: CFRP, cross ply, fatigue, surface treatment, temperature, damage accumulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) is widely applied in aircraft structures. Initially applications were limited to secondary structures, where the static properties such as specific tensile modulus and strength were the most important factors in design. In the 1990s, however, CFRP has been qualified for application in primary aircraft structures, such as fins, stabilisers and floor beams, vital components with respect to the control the aircraft. In these applications, not only are static properties important, but dynamic properties such as fatigue, creep and impact have also become critical factors in design.

One of the most important internal boundaries in composite materials is the interface between fibre and matrix, which plays a major role in the mechanical and physical properties of composites. Furthermore, the effect of environmental temperature is also an important factor for aircraft applications, because aircraft temperatures can fluctuate between approximately -50°C and 80°C during flights. It is, therefore, important to understand how the mechanical properties of carbon fibre composites vary with interface properties and environmental temperature.

This paper presents an investigation of the effects of surface treatment and test temperature on the monotonic and fatigue properties of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy cross ply laminates.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

“Torayca” T800H, a high tensile strength, 5.49 GPa, and intermediate modulus, 294 GPa, type carbon fibre, and Toray resin system #3631, a semitoughened 180°C cure epoxy resin, were used as the basic material for this study. The fibre volume fraction was 0.6. Properties of unidirectional laminates are summarised in Table 1. The laminae of T800H/#3631 were stacked in [0₂/90₄]_S configuration. Specimens 1.6 mm thick, 25 mm wide and with a 120 mm gauge length were carefully polished in both sides with diamond compounds down to 1 μm for optical microscope observations.

Experimental carbon fibres based on the T800H with three different surface treatment levels, untreated, half and double treatment, were used to study the effect of surface treatment. Increasing the level of surface treatment increases the density of functional groups on the fibre surface, producing stronger fibre/resin chemical bonding.

2.2. Methods

An Instron 100kN servohydraulic testing machine, equipped with a chamber within which temperature can be varied, was used. Monotonic and fatigue tests were carried out at room temperature to study the effect of surface treatment using carbon fibres with four different surface treatment levels including standard. Monotonic and fatigue tests were also conducted at low (-40°C) and elevated temperature (100°C) to study the effect of test temperature using carbon fibres with standard surface treatment. For both the monotonic and fatigue tests, the specimen was held for 30 minutes at temperature before starting the test, for the temperature to stabilise. Furthermore preliminary tests to examine the interaction between surface treatment and test temperature were run at 100°C using carbon fibres with three different surface treatments. One specimen was tested for each condition except in the case of the monotonic test with standard surface treatment at room temperature, for which two specimens were used.

Tensile monotonic loading was carried out at a crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min. The loading was stopped at 25MPa intervals in order to monitor the damage accumulation at each stress level. Fatigue tests were conducted with tension-tension loading at a constant stress ratio, $R=0.1$, with a sinusoidal wave form at frequency of 5Hz. The maximum stress level was chosen as 500MPa, the stress level just below that for the initiation of transverse cracks in monotonic tests, for the standard surface treatment, at all temperatures.

Optical microscopy was employed to detect the damage accumulation on the polished side edges of specimens. X-ray radiography was also conducted, using zinc iodide (ZnI_2) dye, at the end of each test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In both monotonic and fatigue tests, the first damage to appear was transverse cracks in 90° plies, as expected from the transverse properties of the unidirectional laminate, as shown in Table 1. On further increase in load or number of fatigue cycles, these cracks grow and increase in number. In some test conditions this is followed by longitudinal cracking in 0° plies, delamination between 0° and 90° plies and fibre fractures.

3.1. Effect of surface treatment

3.1.1. Monotonic tests

Cracking density increased significantly with decreasing surface treatment, as shown in Figure 1(a), which illustrates the effect of surface treatment on the transverse cracking density in monotonic tests at room temperature. Untreated carbon fibre laminates generated transverse cracks during the curing/cooling process before mechanical testing due to the effects of thermal residual stress and the weak fibre/resin adhesion. The initiation stress and saturation density of transverse cracks were increased and decreased, respectively, with higher surface treatment level. The differences in saturation density between untreated and half treatment and in the initiation stress between standard and double treatment were small. Specimen failure strength was lowest with double treated laminates, which failed in a brittle manner with limited pullout.

The number of longitudinal cracks was highest for untreated fibres. Very little delamination was observed in any of the tests.

3.1.2. Fatigue tests

Cracking behaviour in fatigue also varied significantly as a function of the surface treatment. Figure 1(b) shows the effect of surface treatment on the transverse cracking density in fatigue at room temperature. The number of cycles to transverse crack initiation and saturation for the standard treatment was almost the same as for the double treatment, and much higher than for untreated and half treated carbon fibre laminates. The saturation crack density was very similar for the standard and double treatment conditions, at $0.4 - 0.5 \text{ cracks mm}^{-1}$. Similarly, the saturation densities for the untreated and half treated conditions were approximately the same, at about $1.1 \text{ cracks mm}^{-1}$.

The number of longitudinal cracks was also largest in untreated fibres and, as for the monotonic

loading, almost no delamination was observed in all tests.

3.1.3. Comparison of monotonic and fatigue behaviour

For the untreated, half and standard treated fibres very similar damage accumulation behaviour occurs in monotonic loading and fatigue. Approximately the same saturation crack density was attained for both types of loading, ($1.1 \text{ cracks mm}^{-1}$ for untreated and half treated, $0.5 \text{ cracks mm}^{-1}$ for standard), despite the maximum fatigue stress (500 MPa) being below the saturation stress level for monotonic loading in all cases.

The final saturated crack density, the so called characteristic damage state (CDS), predicted by Reifsnider [1] was calculated to be $0.7 \text{ cracks mm}^{-1}$ for half and standard treated laminates using the stiffness data in Table 1. This CDS value should be constant for these laminates which have the same stiffness, ply thickness and stacking sequence, because CDS is predicted to depend on only these three factors. Nevertheless in the case of these experiments the actual saturation densities were quite different at 1.1 and $0.5 \text{ cracks mm}^{-1}$ for these two laminates. This suggests that the CDS value also depends on other parameters, such as fibre/resin adhesion and test temperature.

By contrast, the standard and double treated material show similar fatigue behaviour but markedly different response in monotonic loading. In the monotonic case crack development is strongly retarded in the double treated condition. A larger number of transverse cracks is developed in fatigue because of the resin plastic flow during repeated loading.

3.2. Effect of test temperature

3.2.1. Monotonic tests

The damage accumulation behaviour varied significantly as a function of the test temperature. Figure 2(a) shows the effect of test temperature on the transverse crack density in monotonic tests on material with standard surface treatment. Thermal residual stress is higher at lower temperature because of the greater difference from the curing temperature. The difference in longitudinal thermal residual stress in 90° plies between -40°C and 100°C was predicted to be 35 MPa , using Bailey's equations [2]. Due to the difference in the thermal residual stress, the number of transverse cracks at 100°C was expected to be the lowest, the trend observed by Boniface et al. [3]. In the present experiments the actual number of transverse cracks was largest at 100°C at all stress levels, Figure 2(a). SEM observation of the transverse crack surfaces showed that the amount of resin adhesion on fibre surfaces was less at 100°C than at the lower temperatures, as shown in Figure 3. This change in adhesion appears to explain the large number of transverse cracks at 100°C . An apparent change in adhesion could arise from a number of factors : reduced mechanical clamping, a change in chemical bonding, a marked change in matrix properties.

3.2.2. Fatigue tests

The damage accumulation behaviour was a strong function of the test temperature in fatigue, as well as in monotonic tests, but exhibited a different trend, as shown in Figure 2(b) [5].

The number of cycles to transverse crack initiation and saturation was largest at room temperature. Early initiation and saturation at 100°C are attributed to reduced fibre/resin adhesion as in the monotonic tests. The number of transverse cracks was largest at -40°C in fatigue, although the data lie between that for room temperature and 100°C under monotonic loading.

3.2.3. Comparison of monotonic and fatigue behaviour

Damage accumulation behaviour in monotonic and fatigue tests is summarised in Table 2. The main differences between monotonic and fatigue tests were in the number of transverse cracks at -40°C and the degree of delamination at 100°C .

In both monotonic and fatigue loading the damage accumulation behaviour at room temperature and -40°C shows the effect of temperature observed by Boniface et al. [3], and expected from the increase in thermal residual stress at -40°C . However at 100°C transverse ply cracking develops earlier and to a higher density than would be expected, apparently because of the change in fibre/resin adhesion at this temperature, Figure 3. A change in adhesion would be expected to increase the longitudinal crack density in a similar way to the transverse ply crack density. This effect is shown clearly for the untreated fibre, where both types of cracking increase together. This suggests that the absence of longitudinal cracking at 100°C is associated with a change in transverse ply crack tip geometry. Resin flow blunts the transverse ply crack tips and makes them less effective stress concentrators from the point of view of initiating longitudinal cracking in 0° plies.

Almost complete delamination along the entire specimen occurred at 100°C, as shown in Figure 4, at which temperature no delamination was observed in monotonic tests. Resin plastic flow will occur more severely at high temperature in the resin rich region between 0° and 90° plies because of the low yield stress of neat resin [4]. This appears to be an important factor for delamination under fatigue loading. A creep effect due to the long period of loading at elevated temperature could also be a factor encouraging delamination under fatigue loading.

3.3. Interaction between the effects of surface treatment and test temperature

Preliminary tests between to examine the interaction between surface treatment and test temperature showed that the effect of elevated temperature is dependent on the surface treatment level. Figure 5 shows transverse cracking density in monotonic tests at room temperature and 100°C using the carbon fibres with four different surface treatments including standard treatment. The results suggest that the effect of elevated temperature on fibre/resin adhesion is not a simple mechanical clamping effect of the resin, but that there appears to be an interaction with chemical adhesion. Further tests to examine the interactions between surface treatment, test temperature and resin properties will be the theme of future research.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The damage accumulation behaviour was found to vary significantly as a function of both the test temperature and surface treatment.
- 2) The effects of the temperature and surface treatment on the damage accumulation behaviour were found to be different for monotonic and fatigue loading, particularly in the case of test temperature.
- 3) Surface treatment affected fibre/resin adhesion markedly, but did not affect delamination behaviour.
- 4) Elevated temperature accelerated resin plastic flow in the resin rich region between 0° and 90° plies, causing delamination in fatigue loading.
- 5) Elevated temperature appeared to decrease fibre/resin adhesion, such that damage accumulation was most severe at 100°C.
- 6) Preliminary tests to examine interaction between surface treatment and temperature suggested that the effect of elevated temperature on fibre/resin adhesion is not a simple mechanical clamping effect of the resin.

References

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(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Effect of surface treatment on transverse cracking behaviour at room temperature in (a) monotonic and (b) fatigue tests. For the monotonic tests, the figures in brackets in the key, are the specimen failure stress values in MPa.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Effect of test temperature on transverse cracking behaviour for material with standard surface treatment in (a) monotonic and (b) fatigue tests.

For the monotonic tests, the figures in brackets in the key, are the specimen failure stress values in MPa.

Figure 3. SEM photographs of transverse crack surface on material with standard surface treatment.

(a) after 5.6×10^5 cycles at 100°C

(b) after 1×10^6 cycles at room temperature

(c) after 7×10^5 cycles at -40°C

Figure 4. X-ray radiographs showing damage accumulation in fatigue tests on material with standard surface treatment.

Figure 5. Effect of surface treatment and temperature on transverse cracking behaviour in monotonic tests.
The figures in brackets in the key are the specimen failure stress values in MPa.

Table 1. Unidirectional Laminate Properties ($V_f=0.6$, standard fibre surface treatment).

		Longitudinal	Transverse
Tensile strength	MPa	2840	80
Young's modulus	GPa	160	7.8
Ultimate failure strain	%	1.55	1.0
Coefficient of thermal expansion	$10^{-6}C^{-1}$	0.1	35.5

Table 2. Summary of damage accumulation behaviour in monotonic and fatigue tests.

		-40°C	RT	100°C
MONOTONIC	Transverse	√√	√√√	√√√√
	Longitudinal	√√√	√	0
	Delamination	√	√	0
FATIGUE	Transverse	√√√√	√√	√√√
	Longitudinal	√	√	0
	Delamination	√	√	√√√√√

(√√√√ = severe, 0 = no incidence)